

Factors that influence the impact of public participation in primary health care financing decision-making processes: a protocol for a realist synthesis

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Abstract

This is a protocol for a realist synthesis. The primary research question is: In what circumstances (C) and through what mechanisms (M) does public participation in primary health care financing decision-making processes (I) shape equity of outcomes and responsiveness to community needs (O)?

Sub-questions include:

1. What outcomes have been used to consider the impact of public participation in primary health care (PHC) financing decisions?
2. What are the main context-mechanism-outcome configurations that may explain variation in the effectiveness achieved of direct public participation in PHC financing decisions?
3. What are the attributes of public participation interventions, how are they implemented and what are the related institutional structures that can be measured to assess the progress and influence of public participation?

Background

The processes that determine the allocation and use of public resources

Health financing is about collecting and managing money to pay for health services so people can get the care they need, both individually and as a community. The financing arrangements of health systems determine how much funding the system receives, how resources flow to frontline providers, and the payment systems that create incentives for providers (Hanson et al., 2022). A key element of health financing is public budgeting, which refers to the processes by which governments plan, allocate, and authorize the use of public resources to meet policy priorities (Helene Barroy et al., 2018).

Governments are authorized to collect and spend public money on behalf of constituents. Elected and unelected officials are then accountable to the public for decisions made about the allocation of those resources. One way of legitimizing the decision-making processes connected to the allocation of public monies rests on a role for actors outside of government (e.g., the public, citizens, and residents) in governance decisions. For the public to oversee a decision-making process, the transparency of information related to the decision or process, and information pertaining to the justification of a certain course of action are important instruments for the public to hold decision-makers to account (Daniels and Sabin, 2002; Weale et al., 2016). Opportunities for the public to be involved in the decision-making system can be indirect,¹ through voting in elections where the public designate representatives, or direct, where members of the community are empowered to formulate policy options themselves, i.e., participating in town halls or deliberative forums (Hendriks, 2010: 27).

¹ Other aspects of indirect democracy can be governments engaging advisory groups in decision-making processes.

What do we know about public participation in health financing and budgeting processes?

Direct forms of public participation can range from surveys, public consultations, town hall meetings, to citizen assemblies or deliberative forums. In the context of health financing and budgeting, these mechanisms allow citizens and civil society to influence how public resources are prioritized and allocated. Participatory budgeting is a well-known method of direct participation, where the public and civil society organizations participate directly in influencing fiscal policy (Marquetti et al., 2012). Direct forms of participation aim to give the public a voice in governance decisions. These processes are also argued to foster civic skills and democratic values, which can also enhance the perceived legitimacy of political outcomes (Michels, 2011).

Much empirical evidence on public participation comes from the budgeting literature (Pereira and Figueira, 2022). On the positive side, public participation has been found to improve the information flow between policymakers and taxpayers, facilitating convergence between public preferences and the allocation of public resources (Neshkova and Chen, 2024). Participation in public budgeting is also argued to be an antidote to reduce political alienation by strengthening citizen's engagement between the public and parliamentary fiscal processes (McNulry, 2019: 3). Budgeting processes with public participation can enhance transparency, as greater public scrutiny of financial decisions reduces opportunities for corruption (Chen and Neshkova, 2020; Neshkova and Chen, 2024). In some settings, participatory budgeting has been associated with increased spending on basic services, including sanitation and health-related infrastructure (Gonçalves, 2014).

Despite these potential benefits, evidence suggests that public participation can fall short of transformative goals due to elite capture, inauthentic approaches to including citizens, flaws in design, underfunding, or political interference (Bartocci et al., 2023). Many studies have shown that participatory initiatives do not yield the civic skills and the predicted educational benefits, or at least not equally to all participants (Pereira and Figueira, 2022). Specific to public health, methodological limitations constrain the assessment of impacts on health and wellbeing outcomes making cross-context comparisons of impact difficult (Campbell et al., 2018). A systematic review of co-creation and co-production processes found that most studies focus on the identification of factors that enable participation, while less attention is paid to the specific outcomes of co-creation/ co-production processes, e.g., increases in effectiveness, efficiency, or citizen involvement (Voorberg et al., 2015: 1345).

Financing primary health care: a case for more evidence on the effects of public participation

This realist synthesis focuses on analyzing the impact of *direct* public participation on primary health care (PHC) financing decisions. These exercises include formal processes where members of the public are invited to provide input on service development and provision, examples can include: participatory budgeting, (non)binding voting/referenda, priority setting exercises, or deliberative/participatory fora. Health financing is an area that has shown promise in terms of public participation in decision-making processes, particularly where choices involve trade-offs between competing priorities (Dale E et al., 2023). Engaging the public in health financing decisions, either

through providing advice, or through a more direct form of participation, can help identify public preferences, allowing policy decisions to be better aligned with public priorities (McCoy et al., 2025). Public participation is argued to enhance equity, build trust, strengthen accountability, and promote the sustainability of health financing reforms (Dale E et al., 2023; Bartocci et al., 2023). Related to resource allocation and the purchasing of health services, the area of priority-setting in health has a relatively long track-record of engaging the public in trade-off exercises. For example, the State of Oregon's community meetings in the late 1990s are often cited as an initiative that engaged the public in dialogues about the social values underpinning state health services, highlighting citizens' willingness and ability to engage in ethical trade-offs when the rationales and constraints were transparent (Kitzhaber, 1993; Gutmann and Thompson, 2004: 17-18). Despite such examples, systematic evidence on how public participation influences PHC financing decisions remains limited and inconclusive.

Processes that determine how PHC is financed operate at two interrelated levels: first, the central budget processes that allocates public resources to health vis-à-vis other government priorities; and second, health-sector processes that allocate resources within health – shaping the share that is directed to PHC vis-à-vis hospitals or vertical programs (which tend to be disease-specific with separate funding, management, and goals). Rules on setting budget ceilings, who drafts and negotiates plans, how priorities are assessed, and when (and how) public input occurs all influence whether PHC receives adequate, predictable, and equitable funding. Despite growing global policy attention to PHC financing (Hanson et al., 2022), there remains limited clarity about how participatory health financing processes actually work in practice, how participatory they are, and under what conditions participation is effective and fair (McCollum et al., 2018; Li et al., 2015; Mitton et al., 2009). Studies from devolved settings describe unclear rules for weighing competing claims, constrained technical capacity, and political incentives that favor visible curative projects over preventive and community services, all of factors that can limit the intention of participation (McCollum et al., 2018). Uncertainty also persists regarding how public's views should be weighed against technical, economic, and epidemiological evidence in financing decisions (Mitton et al., 2009).

The evidence on the impact of public participation in PHC financing decisions is fragmented and scattered across diverse contexts, participation interventions and institutional arrangements. For example, a study of public engagement in priority setting within a Primary Care Trust in England found that the participation exercises had minimal impact on subsequent resource allocation decisions (Williams et al., 2014). Similarly, in coastal Kenya, health facility committees intended to incorporate community voice into facility financing gained responsibility to influence allocations of user-fee revenues and direct facility funding. However, variable awareness, skills, and perceived authority about health financing committees amongst community members were attributed to constrain their impact on PHC-oriented allocations (Goodman et al., 2011).

In Tanzania, Direct Health Facility Financing strengthened the formal roles of Health Facility Governing Committees' roles in planning, budgeting, and oversight – yet their effectiveness

depended heavily on clear mandates, training, and accountability linkages upward and downward (Kesale et al., 2022). In Nigeria, accountability arrangements under the Basic Health Care Provision Fund mapped multiple oversight actors and instruments intended to safeguard PHC funds, while also highlighting risks of elite capture, implementation delays, and weak transparency when participation mechanisms were poorly operationalized (Uzochukwu et al., 2020).

Framings of public participation by international agencies often start from a normative position that more participation is better (OECD, 2020; WHO, 2021). However, the empirical evidence base remains fragmented across contexts and participatory instruments, including devolution, direct facility financing committees, and earmarked PHC funds. Additionally, public participation in health is not costless. Participatory processes include staff expertise and time, diverting financial and human resources from health services (Dale et al., 2024; Voogdt-Pruis et al., 2025). Given the contradicting evidence on the effects of public participation, this realist synthesis aims to generate a theory-informed understanding of what, how, why, for whom, and to what extent, do public participation interventions in PHC financing work achieve – or fail to achieve – equitable and responsive outcomes. A synthesis across this literature will add value by identifying the features of process design (e.g., budgeting rules, timing, information disclosure), actor capacities (technical, political, community), and accountability arrangements –by linking those features to observable financing decisions and PHC outcomes.

Research questions of the synthesis

The primary research question of the realist synthesis is: In what circumstances (C) and through what mechanisms (M) does public participation in primary health care financing decision-making processes (I) shape equity of outcomes and responsiveness to community needs (O)?

Sub-questions include:

1. What outcomes have been used to consider the impact of public participation in primary health care (PHC) financing decisions?
2. What are the main context-mechanism-outcome configurations that may explain variation in the effectiveness achieved of direct public participation in PHC financing decisions?
3. What are the attributes of public participation interventions, how are they implemented and what are the related institutional structures that can be measured to assess the progress and influence of public participation?

Theory development

In realist syntheses, initial program theories are developed to describe how and why an intervention is expected to work, for whom, and in what contexts (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2012; Jagosh, 2019). This realist synthesis aims to generate a theory-informed understanding of when, how, and why public participation in PHC financing achieves – or fails to achieve – equitable and responsive outcomes. In this realist synthesis, we define equitable outcomes at two levels. At the level of the public participation intervention, an equitable outcome is one in which the intervention increases the representation of community members and populations experiencing different degrees of

disadvantage (economic, social, geographic, racial, etc.) in decision-making. At the level of the PHC financing decision, an equitable outcome is one in which resources are allocated in ways that benefit populations experiencing different degrees of disadvantage (economic, social, geographic, racial, etc.). We similarly define responsiveness at two levels. At the level of the **public participation intervention**, responsiveness is defined as treating people with respect and upholding their rights (Khan et al., 2021; Mirzoev et al., 2025). At the level of the **PHC financing decision**, responsiveness is defined as allocating resources in line with needs identified by community members and the public, thereby meeting people's expectations of the decision-making process.

The initial program theories outline the assumed causal pathways linking context, intervention, mechanisms, and outcomes – providing a basis for exploring variation in how interventions produce effects. For this realist synthesis, the context -, intervention, mechanism -and outcome (CIMO) configuration is defined as follows:

Context: across different countries and factors beyond the public participation intervention that can *influence the mechanisms* which create PHC financing outcomes. For this study, examples of context can include governance conditions of the setting or the accessibility or inclusiveness of the process.

Intervention: Public participation processes related to PHC financing in any country at all levels of government. For this study, examples of interventions can be public consultations, policy dialogues, mini-publics, or prioritization exercises.

Mechanism: The underlying *processes and responses triggered by the intervention* that influence decisions or uptake of advice resulting from public participation in a PHC financing decision-making process. For this study, an example of a mechanism could for a Health Facility Committee deciding to allocate funds in a certain way, following a public participation intervention (Goodman et al., 2011).

Outcome: The intended or unintended effects arising from context-mechanism interactions as a result of the intervention. For this study, outcome can include greater allocation of resources to PHC.

As part of this protocol development, we formulated a set of theoretical statements reflecting our assumptions about when and how public participation interventions lead to equitable and responsive outcomes by participants. Initial program theories were informed by empirical literature and major reports on public participation and public budgeting:

- Reports from international agencies, such as: (United Nations, 2005; OECD, 2020; WHO, 2021; World Bank, 2023)
- Empirical literature exploring the impacts of public participation during public budgeting
- Use of an artificial intelligence search engine (i.e., Perplexity.ai) was used during the development of initial program theories to generate summaries and program theories as a starting point for our deeper inquiry and synthesis

- Insights from subject-matter experts.

In realist synthesis, the program theories are iteratively tested and refined as additional evidence is identified and analyzed to explore how an intervention, in this case, public participation, produces different outcomes across contexts, with the theory continuously refined as additional evidence is examined. This realist synthesis aims to distinguish between contextual factors that are difficult to modify in the short-term (e.g., political culture, inequality) and those that may be more actionable (e.g., process design, civic education, resource support). By doing so, the synthesis aims to inform the practical use of public participation in resource allocation decisions.

Initial program theories

Clear procedural rules, transparent decision-making structures, and public reporting mechanisms build trust among participants and reduce the risk of manipulation (Fung, 2006). Oversight structures, such as public monitoring committees and the publication of budget reports, further strengthen accountability and credibility in budget processes (Wampler, 2000; Wampler and Touchton, 2019). This emphasizes a framing of public participation as part of “good governance” highlighting the importance of the managerial aspects of public governance. Referring to technical and managerial language, rather than rights-based language more commonly used under “Participation as a political-electoral connection” (Pereira and Figueira, 2022).

- *If PHC financing decision-making processes with public participation (I) are transparent and follow clear procedural rules (C1) and are accessible to the public (C2) then the public are more likely to accept or trust the process (M) and are more likely to participate (O).*

Direct participation in budgeting processes tend to promote equity when they are designed to enable participation from a broad cross-section of the population, especially marginalized and underserved groups (Holdo, 2020; Pape and Lerner, 2016). When participation is dominated by more privileged groups, however, the process may reinforce existing inequalities (Kuenneke and Scutelnicu, 2021).

- *When governance allows for a more inclusive and representative group of the community (C) to be involved in participatory processes (I), a variety of perspectives will be considered (M), and the outcomes or decisions are therefore more likely to be responsive to the communities priorities (O).*
- *If members of the public who are facing different forms of social and economic disadvantage (C) are directly involved in PHC financing processes (I), then they are more likely to be aware of distributional consequences (M) and will therefore be more responsive to community identified needs (O).*

Public participation interventions are more likely to achieve meaningful outcomes when supported by government actors who legitimize the process and champion citizen involvement. Institutional support – particularly from public administration – is critical for implementation (Fung, 2006). Conversely, a lack of political commitment or active resistance from political elites often results in superficial or symbolic participation, undermining the process from the outset.

- *If public participation processes related to PHC financing (I) are implemented in settings with political support for public participation in policymaking (C1) and where decision-makers are more likely to listen to, engage with communities (C2), then decision-makers will recognize the importance of public input and will justify resulting decisions (M). Such interactions will improve the public's acceptance of trade-offs necessary in PHC financing decision-making (O)*
- *If there is a lack of legislative mandate or willingness of decision-makers (C) to include public participation in PHC financing processes (I), then participatory processes will be inconsistent, ad-hoc, and vulnerable to elite capture and corrupt influence (M), which can contribute to decisions that are less responsive to community identified needs (O).*
- *If sub-national decision-makers have limited discretionary spending authority within PHC financing decisions (C), then public participation processes related to PHC financing (I) will generate limited negotiation power to change the allocation of resources (M), resulting in little influence on PHC service resource allocation decisions (O).*

For citizens to meaningfully engage in budgeting decisions, they must have access to relevant, comprehensible information (Schugurensky et al., 2021). Capacity-building efforts – including education on budgeting processes and training in deliberative methods – can empower participants, particularly those with less formal education or political experience (Schugurensky et al., 2021). Without such support, participation may remain superficial or skewed toward more informed actors.

- *If there is a culture of sharing information with communities about PHC financing processes (C) in public participation process (I) communities will be better informed about procedurally fair decision-making processes (M). Then it is more likely that the public can meaningfully engage in such public participation processes (O).*

The effectiveness of participatory budgeting also depends on the extent and nature of the resources made available. Adequate financial, human, and logistical resources are needed to support outreach, facilitation, and project implementation. Additionally, when only small or discretionary portions of the budget are subject to participation, the impact on equity and service responsiveness is inherently limited.

- *If participation in public budgeting activities related to resource allocation decisions for PHC services (I) include compensation for community members time (C) encouraging that a wider representative group to be included in the participatory process (M), then it is more likely that participation will reflect a representative sample of the community the PHC services are intended to serve (O).*

This is a non-exhaustive list of initial program theories that outline some of the ‘hunches’ that we have identified at the beginning of the realist synthesis process (Peters, 2025). The initial program theories will be further refined, and new theories may be added as a result of the realist synthesis process.

Key concepts

The following key concepts are relevant to this realist synthesis (Table 1).

Table 1: Key concepts

Concept	Explanation
The public	The public is largely made up of citizens (although some members of the public such as refugees and recent immigrants may not be recognized as citizens). Support for greater public involvement generally draws on democratic theory and principles of citizenship. Citizenship includes the core features of rights, duties, participation and identity and the role of citizen is based on the legitimacy of legal, political and social membership of the community, making political participation – activities intended to influence government action but not necessarily targeting political authorities – an important part of citizenship (Fredriksson and Tritter, 2017: 98). Patients are a subset of the public whose interests usually reflect their role as service users, whereas citizens are seen as members of the public concerned with broader societal interests (Fredriksson and Tritter, 2017: 95).
Public participation	Public participation is viewed as a process by which the government actively seeks out the public’s views and inputs with regard to a decision or a way of civil society to influence the political agenda (WHO, 2021: 12).
Primary Health Care (PHC)	PHC is defined as a platform, which includes both community-level and first-level health care (Hanson et al., 2022). Primary care is the first level of a health system where people present their health problems and where the majority of the population’s curative health needs, health promotion and preventive health needs are satisfied (Starfield, 1994). Our understanding of PHC includes all resources – infrastructure, workforce, and related decisions.
Health financing	Health financing is about who is asked to pay, when they pay, and how the money raised is spent. This realist synthesis follows WHO’s approach to health financing which focuses on core functions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - revenue raising (sources of funds, including government budgets, compulsory or voluntary prepaid insurance schemes, direct out-of-pocket payments by users, and external aid) - pooling of funds (the accumulation of prepaid funds on behalf of some or all of the population) - purchasing of services (the payment or allocation of resources to health service providers) (WHO, 2025)
Primacy Health Care financing decisions	Decisions that relate to the revenue raising, pooling of funds and purchasing of PHC services, including decisions related to human resources.
Realist synthesis	A synthesis of information that goes beyond amassing the patterns in the data, and instead searching for explanation. Realist review seeks to unpack the relationships between context, mechanism and outcomes - i.e. how particular contexts have ‘triggered’ (or interfered with) mechanisms to generate the observed outcomes (Greenhalgh et al., 2011). (Dixon-Woods et al., 2005).

Concept	Explanation
Context (M)	The contextual conditioning of a causal mechanism which turns (or fails to turn) a causal potential into a causal outcome (Pawson and Tilley, 1997: 69). Context refers to things that affect whether and which mechanisms operate - which is how they affect outcomes. (e.g., demographics, legislation, cultural norms...)
Intervention (I)	“... Intervention X (for example, a program introduced by policymakers who seek to create a particular outcome) alters context (for example, by making new resources available), which then triggers mechanism(s), which produce both intended and unintended outcomes. Intervention X may work well in one context but poorly or not at all in another context (Wong et al., 2013).
Mechanism (M)	Program mechanisms (i) reflect the embeddedness of the program within the stratified nature of social reality; (ii) take the form of propositions which will provide an account of how macro and micro processes constitute the program; (iii) demonstrate how program outputs follow from the stakeholders’ choices (reasoning) and their capacity (resources) to put these into practice (Pawson and Tilley, 1997: 66). A theory which spells out the potential of human resources and reasoning (Pawson and Tilley, 1997: 68)
Outcome (O)	The result of the mechanism activating in context. Intended or unintended effects based on context-mechanism interactions (Jagosh, 2019). (e.g., impact of the public participation mechanism, decision -making output, decision uptake, arrangements that recognize and reflect input from the public...).
Responsiveness	Health systems responsiveness entails an actual experience of people’s interaction with their health system, which confirms or disconfirms their initial expectations (Mirzoev and Kane, 2017)
Equitable outcome	An equitable outcome is one in which the intervention increases the representation of community members and populations experiencing different degrees of disadvantage (economic, social, geographic, racial, etc.) in decision-making. At the level of the PHC financing decision, an equitable outcome is one in which resources are allocated in ways that benefit populations experiencing different degrees of disadvantage (economic, social, geographic, racial, etc.).
Abductive thinking	The concept of abduction implies a mode of reasoning distinct from deductive and inductive thinking that affords the construction or generation of truly novel explanations (Ritz, 2020). A form of inventive and intuitive (‘hunch-driven’) thinking that allows a researcher to creatively imagine, for example, potential mechanisms to be investigated (Klingberg et al., 2021; Jagosh et al., 2014).

Methods

Rationale for using realist synthesis

Realist synthesis is a method which is useful to help draw causal explanations for complex interventions (Pawson et al., 2005; Wong et al., 2013). The methodology was chosen to uncover how, and for whom and under what circumstances public participation in PHC financing decisions work. The realist method enables researchers to develop “... a picture of the research *contexts* in which

particular investigative *mechanisms* work best to generate the desired methodological *outcomes* (Pawson and Tilley, 1997: 215). This protocol sets out the scope for this realist synthesis, describing draft program theories, and the methods for searching and identifying data, selection of studies, data extraction, analysis and reporting. As realist syntheses are iterative, the following description is an initial outline of the proposed approach, which may be modified during the process. The protocol will be updated with changes made during the synthesis process following finalization of the synthesis.

Scoping and sources of literature

Our main source for literature will be peer-reviewed articles identified through a systematic search (see below). To supplement this search, we will conduct a targeted search to identify data on public participation in PHC financing processes, focusing especially on grey literature (e.g., seminal reports, program evaluations, and program websites) from international agencies and non-governmental agencies (e.g., World Bank, International Budget Partnership). We will also consider country-specific literature, focusing on literature from Kenya and Tanzania where the research team will conduct empirical studies on public participation in PHC financing and countries represented in the Exemplars in Global Health project (Exemplars in global health coalition, 2021).

We will also consider literature recommended by members of the Promoting Responsiveness and Equity for Primary Health Care Decisions through Voice (ProtEqVoice) research team and Advisory Group.

Searching processes

Literature searching will be both systematic and iterative. To identify relevant literature and inform the search strategy, we will also conduct an initial identification of relevant literature answering the research questions using the AI-tool Perplexity (Perplexity.ai, 2025). The systematic searching will be from the following electronic databases (e.g., MEDLINE, Ovid (1946 to date of search), Embase, Ovid (conference proceedings) (1947 to date of search), CINAHL, EBSCOhost (1961 to date of search) SCOPUS, Elsevier (2004 to date of search), Web of Science and Epistemonikos (www.epistemonikos.org) (Epistemonikos Foundation).

Additionally, we will supplement systematic searches with iterative searching, which allows us to include literature from diverse sources. Iterative searches will include reference mining, where we search the references of relevant articles, and citation tracking, to identify studies that have cited relevant literature. We will use *Citationchaser* to assist with this (Haddaway NR et al., 2022).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Table 2 describes the inclusion and exclusion criteria that will be used to include studies in the realist synthesis. In line with realist synthesis methods, the following inclusion and exclusion criteria may be refined in light of the emerging data and as programme theories are refined (Hunter et al., 2022).

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Study types	Qualitative or quantitative empirical studies published in a scientific article, scoping review, systematic review, commentary, report, book chapter, PhD thesis, doctoral dissertation, study protocol, systematic or scoping review.	Conference proceedings and abstracts.
Phenomenon under study	In the title or abstract, explicit mention of public participation in any PHC financing process, decision, policy, or funding arrangement	No explicit mention of outcomes Lack of data on public participation in the process Studies that focus on public participation in decisions related to medicines.
Language	All.	
Time	From 1990	

Testing of initial program theories

The initial program theories were discussed internally among the ProtEqVoice research team who were engaged in developing the protocol. We also discussed the initial program theories and basic assumptions guiding our understanding of the relationship between public participation, PHC financing and key outcomes in a digital consultation with the ProtEq Voice advisory group and subsequent follow-up with individual experts.

Selection and appraisal of documents

Two review authors will independently assess the titles and abstracts of the identified records against the eligibility criteria. The priority screening ranking algorithm of EPPI-Reviewer, a web-based software program for managing and analyzing data in literature reviews, will be used for title and abstract screening to prioritize studies for review. This machine learning strategy continuously learns from researcher decisions, prioritizing the most relevant studies to be screened first (Gates et al., 2019). Studies will be included if they meet our inclusion criteria (see table 2). For studies written in a language not understood by the members of the review group, translation software (e.g., google translate or Chat GPT) will be used. Grey literature will not be added to EPPI-Reviewer, and will be instead read separately. After identifying all eligible studies (peer reviewed and grey), sampling may be used if the volume of studies meeting the inclusion criteria is deemed too extensive. In such cases a maximum variation purposive sampling will be used that will consider country context (income and geographic), participation intervention, PHC financing decision, governance setting, and other relevant contextual factors (Ames et al., 2019).

Data extraction, categorization and synthesis process

For the data extraction we will read the entire text of each data source to identify relevant information from all sections of each source. A standardized extraction form will be used, where we will extract

general information about the data source, including: study aims, type of article (research article, report, commentary). We will also extract characteristics relevant to our study aim, these include a description of the public participation intervention (including relevant characteristics, such as: advice-giving, decision-making etc..) and how it relates to PHC financing. We will also extract the level of government where the decision is made (e.g., national, sub-national) and what aspect of the PHC system that the decision relates to (e.g., governance, service delivery), attributes of effective public participation programs, and other distinguishable characteristics of the PHC program and financing instrument. In terms of causal theories and identification of mechanisms, we will extract evidence related to the impact of distribution and allocation of funds to PHC, and any documented influence of public participation. To align with the realist methodology, no methodological quality assessment will be conducted.

The synthesis process will combine an inductive and deductive approach, where review authors will be guided by initial program theories and will also refine, or develop new program theories. We have adapted the following three-step approach to realist data extraction and analysis (Danermark et al., 2019). **Step 1 (Description)**, we will search relevant passages for descriptions of public participation that has had an impact on PHC financing decisions and any documented information on possible effectiveness. Guided by similar reviews, we will anticipate that hypotheses will be provided in the motivation of a study, in the methods section as research hypotheses, or in the discussion or conclusion section to provide possible explanations for unexpected research outcomes. Evidence is often provided in the results section (Döbbling-Hildebrandt et al., 2025). Quotes will be copied from the data source and be added to the data extraction form, which will also include a summary of the review authors' interpretation and argument for why the intervention may have, or have not, worked. Those findings relating to outcomes will be coded as 'outcomes'. **Step 2 (Analysis)**, we will break down the phenomenon into core components and relations, adhering to the core concepts of realism to a generative explanation for causation - that is, an outcome (O) of interest was generated by relevant mechanism(s) (M) being triggered in context (C) (Wong et al., 2013). **Step 3 (Abduction)** where we will use theories to make sense of the data (Klingberg et al., 2021; Jagosh et al., 2014; Braun and Clarke, 2021). The refining of program theories will start with the initial program theories we have described above. Throughout this process we will identify the possible reasoning or rationales that can describe how, and for whom and under what circumstances public participation has had an effect on PHC financing processes, decisions, policies, or funding arrangements.

Reporting of data

Following the three-step process, we will report as CMO configurations, where the data will be reported against the RAMESES (Realist And Meta-narrative Evidence Syntheses – Evolving Standards) publication standards (Wong et al., 2013).

End-user engagement

The end-users of this realist synthesis include civil society and policymakers across levels of healthcare in all countries and/or settings. We also aim to communicate with researchers interested in questions related to health systems, democratic theory, or related fields. And public financial

management experts. End-user consultation will be facilitated by partners in Kenya, Tanzania, and through members of the advisory group.

Reflexivity statement

Reflexivity in qualitative research is actively examining how researchers' experiences, positions, contexts, and biases influence the research process and its outcomes (Braund et al., 2024). The review team is made up of (14) researchers. Of which (5) are female and (9) are male. Twelve co-authors originate from LMICs (Kenya, Tanzania and Kyrgyzstan). The remainder have familial roots from India, New Zealand and Norway. Eleven are affiliated with research institutions, and three are affiliated with a non-profit organizations.

The authors hold a diverse range of expertise that can be broadly described as relating to health systems, health financing, or public financing. Some co-authors also have clinical backgrounds in medicine, and nursing. Specific to public participation, some members represent an advocacy institution that works to advance transparency, accountability, participation, and equity in national and sub-national budgeting processes. Other experiences were primarily research-focused, including observing county-level public participation in budgets and engaging PHC facility committees and have completed some commissioned in country evaluations of such interventions.

At the beginning of the synthesis, the research team shared several key perspectives and beliefs regarding the topic of the synthesis. All review team members were asked to describe any assumptions about the outcomes of the research and the findings, using the prompts of Braund et al. All members of the research group were consulted in the development of the initial program theories that reflect some of the theoretical assumptions about when and how public participation interventions lead to desirable outcomes in PHC financing. Firstly, we all shared a normative position that the public ought to have access to information about the decision-making processes that relate to the allocation of public monies. This view aligns with literatures of procedural justice and democratic theory, as described in the Background of this protocol.

This synthesis is part of a wider research project, ProtEqt Voice. The conceptual framing of this project is that transparent, participatory and inclusive decision-making processes at central and sub-national levels can support responsive and equitable health systems with strong PHC. However, the origin of this synthesis stems from inconclusiveness in the literature on whether participation leads to responsive and equitable outcomes. As a research group, we do not believe that more public participation in PHC will automatically be linked to good governance, recognizing that it may not always be feasible, nor appropriate, for members of the public to be engaged in decision-making processes. In these instances, the oversight of decision-making processes and its outputs can be an important way for the public to observe the fairness of decision-making processes.

Other assumptions about the outcomes of the research were that even inclusive participation processes (e.g. reimbursements for time) may inadvertently exclude certain groups due to the public nature of these forums (e.g., requiring a certain level of public speaking skills). Review authors expressed a hunch that the sustainability of some public participation interventions may be hindered

by non-profits being the main implementors, meaning that governments may not take ownership of these fora. There was recognition that the effectiveness of participation interventions are dynamic, context-dependent, and shaped by informal rules and principal–agent power dynamics more than by formal policy. Some personal experiences highlighted the constraints off effective public participation, including: being constrained by political sensitivities, power asymmetries between health managers and community boards, low education among facility committee members, and funding gaps that disrupt regular meetings – often reducing engagement to nominal involvement. On the positive side, a belief was shared that emphasized the social accountability aspects of participation, emphasizing that there are opportunities to scrutinize budgets within countries, and deepen genuine participation which can meaningfully influence public finance decisions.

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